

The GMT-Consortium Large Earth Finder (G-CLEF): An optical echelle spectrograph for the Giant Magellan Telescope (GMT) with multi-object spectroscopy (MOS) capability.

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for the G-CLEF collaboration

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The G-CLEF Collaboration

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First ... An Infomercial

- Optical/NIR capability
 - 0.3 – 25 μ
- Primary dia. – 25.4m
 - 7 x 8.4 m primary segments
 - 7 x 1.1 m secondaries
 - Prim/2ndary conjugation
- Primary – f/0.7
- Net focal ratio – f/8
 - Plate scale 1mm = 1 arcsec
- FOV
 - 10 arcmin uncorrected
 - 20 arcmin w/corrector
- Adaptive optics are intrinsic
 - Fewest possible reflections
 - Very low thermal contamination
 - Always available to all instruments
- **Four-Mirror First Light 2023**

The GMT-Consortium Large Earth Finder (G-CLEF) properties:

- Fiber-fed optical echelle spectrograph
- General purpose instrument
- Precision radial velocity (PRV) capable
- The first light science instrument for the GMT
- Passband is 3500Å – 9000Å (Spec) / 9500Å (Goal)
- Operates in 4 resolution modes
- **Has an interface to MANIFEST for MOS operation**

See: Lawrence et al. 9908-358 This conference, (Today).

Mode	PRV	NS-PRV	MR	HT	MOS
Resolution	108,000	108,000	35,000	19,000	35,000

PRV: Precision Radial Velocity Mode
NS-PRV: Non-scrambled PRV Mode

MR: Medium Resolution Mode
HT: High Throughput Mode

G-CLEF System Design

- G-CLEF Front End Assembly (GCFEA)
- G-CLEF spectrograph (GCSPECT)
- Multi-Object Spectroscopy feed (MANIFEST)
- Calibration Light Source (GCCLS)
- Science fiber feed assembly (GCSFIB)
- Calibration fiber feed assembly (GCCFIB)

G-CLEF Location on GMT

Surrounding Scene Folded to Flexure Control Sys.

Science Object Injected into Science Fibers

Spectrograph Thermal Control Panels

Spectrograph Vacuum Enclosure

Vacuum Enclosure

Vacuum Pump
System

Composite Optical
Bench

G-CLEF Optical Bench Rib Structure

- Asymmetric white pupil design
- 7 Element red camera, 8 element red camera
- One asphere in each camera
- Mangin mirror correct intrinsic cylindrical field curvature

See: Ben-Ami et al., 2016 SPIE (Edinburgh)

Current G-CLEF Optical Bench Design

Optical bench is made of composite material with extremely low coefficient of thermal expansion, high thermal conductivity & low mass to stiffness ratio to minimize thermally induced flexure and reduce mass.

See: Mueller, et al., 2016, SPIE, (Edinburgh)
and Baldwin et al., 2016, SPIE, (Edinburgh)

G-CLEF Mounted in Vacuum Vessel

G-CLEF is vacuum enclosed to insulate the spectrograph thermally and stabilize the index of refraction of the immersing medium to maximize radial velocity measurement precision. The vacuum vessel is made of aluminum.

... from the perspective of calibration?

- Ultra precise radial velocity measurement is an intrinsic capability of G-CLEF
- For a while G-CLEF will have largest aperture (= S/N) among PRV instruments, but ...
- ESO/Geneva teams have pioneered “modern” calibration sources:
 - Laser frequency combs
 - Ultrastable etalons
- Talks by Pepe, LoCurto & Wu at this workshop are comprehensive
- G-CLEF isn't built yet – no data, only predictions
- What's left to talk about?

Thank You. Questions?

G-CLEF Precision RV Budgeting Approach

PRV BUDGET STRUCTURE

Built on works of Gibson and Howard, e.g. Howard 2014 EPRV Workshop Presentations
PRV Budget has been critical to cost/benefit analysis, e.g. for composite optical bench
See: Podgorski, 2014 Proc SPIE (Montreal), 9147

G-CLEF Will Have MOS Capability

- Multiplex advantage of 40-50
- $R \sim 40,000$
- 20 arcmin diameter patrol field
- Useful for abundances, internal dynamics of globular clusters & dSph, coarse exoplanet RV studies
- Design parameters will be optimized over next year

Configuration	Field of view	Instruments
Direct Gregorian Narrow Field	10 arcmin	Wide-field spectrograph
Folded Port	3 arcmin	High-resolution spectrograph Adaptive optics instruments
Direct Gregorian Wide Field	20 arcmin	MANIFEST fiber feed

MOS

MANY Instrument FibEr positioning SysTem (MANIFEST)

- Starbugs consist of co-axial piezoelectric tubes
- Optical payload installed at centre of inner tube
- Vacuum is applied between tubes
- All services through a single connector for each Starbug providing modular unit

See Lawrence et al., 2016, Proc SPIE (Edinburgh), 9908

- Hectochelle – 300 fiber multiobject echelle deployed at the MMT
- $R = 40,000$, First light 2003, PRV capable - PLDP* $\sim 15 \text{ m/s}^{**}$
- 1st light calibration system design – ThAr HCL return off dome screen

Cal lamp
system

- Attenuation from dome return into f/5 fiber system is 10^{-13} *
- Calibration scheme “impossible” – low signal to noise with hour-long integration.
- Reconfigured 18 lamp cal lamp system to point directly into focal plane.
- “Good” S/N in 20-30 minutes, adequate S/N in 5 minutes.

- Telecentricity is essential for efficient optical fiber feed producing good wavelength solution.
- Telecentric fiber feed requires fiber point at exit pupil.
- Cassegrain design → exit pupil is virtual, far behind secondary.
- No “real” telecentric location for calibration source.
- Calibration source must be located in front of secondary.
- Calibration light beam is very non-telecentric.
- Calibration highly fiber position-dependent.
- RV calibration is poor → 300-500 m/s systematics.
- Obtained ~200 m/s with restrictive operational protocols.

Cramer et al., 2008

Tunable Laser Implementation

- Tunable lasers lock is inadequate ~few km/sec precision.
- Off-the shelf wavemeters capable of 2 ppm precision

Tunable laser (w/ Claire Cramer)

Tunable laser return off MMT dome screen and MMT secondary

Wavelength Solution with Tunable Laser

Wavelength solution for a single fiber containing Ca IR triplet (8500Å)

Wavelength Solution Residuals with Tunable Laser

Wavelength solution exhibits systematic that is fitted out

Tunable Laser Calibration 5x Better Than ThAr

FWHM ~ 400 m/s

ThAr Residuals

FMHW ~ 80 m/s

Tunable Laser Residuals

- Residuals histogrammed are per feature
- ~ 150 usable features/order
- Achievable RV per object ($80/\sqrt{150} \sim 7$ m/s)
- Further optimization could improve this precision

Tunable Laser Calibration Frame

ThAr Calibration Frame

Near Ca IR Triplet (8500Å)

- No scattered light from bright Ar features
- Very bright → very short calibration times
- Operating range 3500Å – NIR
- Commercial Off the Shelf, relatively simple to operate
- Pitch of emission features is arbitrarily tunable unlike frequency combs

Considerations for the GMT

- The baseline GMT wide field corrector design is extremely telecentric
- Departure from telecentricity < 1 arcmin over 20' field of view
- GMT is Gregorian
 - Provide real internal focus \rightarrow location of cal system
- Wide field of MANIFEST requires large diameter calibration screen
 - Primary diameter = 25.4m, Primary f/# = f/0.7
 - $\Phi_{\text{Cal screen}} = 25.4 \times 0.7 \times 20 \times 60 \times 5 \times 10^{-6} = 107 \text{ mm}$
- However, for moderate RV precision ($\sim 15 - 30 \text{ m/s}$)
 - ThAr lamps will not be adequate
 - Laser frequency combs may not be optimal
- Tunable lasers may be optimal calibrators for high dispersion multiobject spectroscopy.

 GIANT MAGELLAN
TELESCOPE

GMT Site Drone Movie Late-2016

GMT Site Drone Movie Late-2016

MANIFEST on GMT

Science Case		
1	Period of peak stellar formation in galaxies	9.1.3
2	Massive galaxy Assembly / AGN	9.1.3
3	Evolution of galaxy clustering	9.1.3
4	IGM Tomography	9.2.3
5	Dark Matter Distribution	9.2.3
6	Reionization & First Lights	9.1.3
7	Local Group Archaeology (including our Galaxy)	9.3.3

Button Configurations		
# Starbugs		FOV
65	19	1.25"
14	2	0.75"
14	91	2.75"
1	1300	9"
420	19	1"
1	8400	23"
43	3	0.7"

	TAIPAN	MANIFEST
Num. Starbugs	150-300	200-1000+
Num. fibres	150-300	>4000
Field of View	6 degrees	20 arcmins
Field ROC	3 m	3.3 m
Field diameter	335 mm	1300mm
Payload	Single fibre	IFU
Focal ratio	f/2.5	f/8
Instruments int.	Single	Multiple
Telescope int.	Fixed	Deployable

- Provides high res, wide FOV, high multiplex
- CDP will commence in 2017